

HOME OFFICE SECURITY & POLICING EVENT 2025

Main Authors

Helen Gibson (CENTRIC)
Cyril Piotrowicz (FRMDLI)

July 2025

About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

Report Feedback

We’re collecting feedback on this report through the EU Survey Platform, if you’d like to share your thoughts anonymously please click on the link below.

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/enact-report-feedback>

**Funded by
the European Union**

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright

This report contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Acronyms

CBRNE	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear and Explosive
DSTL	Defence Science and Technology Laboratory
EU	European Union
FCN	Forensic Capability Network
JSaRC	Joint Security and Resilience Centre
LEDS	Law Enforcement Data Service
NCA	National Crime Agency
NaCTSO	National Counter Terrorism Security Office
PNR	Passenger Name Records
SICUR	International Security, Safety and Fire Exhibition
UK	United Kingdom

Home Office Security & Policing 2025: Overview

The Home Office Security & Policing [1] exhibition in Farnborough is the second biggest event for Security professionals in the United Kingdom. The 2025 edition gathered over 430 exhibitors from 25 countries [2], over 9,600 visitors, and a speaker programme with 60 briefings and panels, ahead of the International Security Expo 2024 [3] held in London (350 exhibitors and 10,000 visitors) and behind The Security Event 2025 [4] (450 exhibitors and 16,500 visitors). This event is organised by United Kingdom's Home Office [5], in collaboration with the Joint Security and Resilience Centre (JSaRC) [6], Dods [7], ADS [8] and United Kingdom Defence and Security Exports (UK DSE) [9].

While sharing the same intent as other security events, such as SICUR, TECNOSEC, DRONEXPO and EUROSATORY, which ENACT actively tracks to produce flash reports [10], Security & Policing is a closed-door event where attendance is granted individually by the United Kingdom Home Office. Its closed format ensures a **secure, trust-based environment** where sensitive technologies and operational needs can be discussed freely - something that public trade shows cannot offer. For governments, it enables confidential exchanges on procurement, capability gaps, and regulatory priorities. For researchers and innovators, it offers an exclusive space to present advanced prototypes, engage in horizon scanning, and explore co-development opportunities with end-users. For equipment manufacturers, it provides access to strategic buyers and technical decision-makers from across the UK and allied countries. These live demos enable attendees to evaluate the functionality, integration, and operational relevance of the solution before deployment. Security & Policing is not just a showcase - it is a **critical interface** where future-ready technologies meet national and international security priorities in a controlled, outcome-oriented setting.

[1] <https://www.securityandpolicing.co.uk/>

[2] Number of exhibitors is based on the latest version of the exhibitor guide and includes all exhibitors listed, country is based on the address listed in the exhibitor guide.

[3] <https://www.internationalsecurityexpo.com//portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/ISFP-2019-AG-DRUGS>

[4] <https://www.thesecurityevent.co.uk/>

[5] <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/home-office>

[6] <https://www.jsarc.org.uk/>

[7] <https://www.dodspoliticalintelligence.com/>

[8] <https://www.adsgroup.org.uk/>

[9] <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/uk-defence-and-security-exports>

[10] <https://enact-eu.net/results/>

For this 2025 edition, the exhibition revolved around 26 categories for the products and services offered, aiming to foster cooperation and ease the targeting of relevant exhibitors:

Access Control and Entry Systems	Fire/First Response
Biometrics, Facial Recognition & Imagery	Forensic Services
Border and Maritime Security	Information Technology
CBRNE	Incident & Emergency Response
CCT & Video Analytics	Optics
Comms Data and Digital Forensics	Personal Protection Equipment, Clothing & Accessories
Communications, Command & Control	Physical Security, Man-guarding & Close Protection
Counter Explosive Ordnance, Explosives & Blast Protection	Professional Services
Counter Terrorism & Intelligence	Protective and Transport Packaging
Covert Operations & Capabilities	Training
Custodial	Transport Security
Cyber Security	Unmanned Systems, Robotics & Countermeasures
Data acquisition and analysis	Vehicles

Organisations exhibiting showed strong alignment with the areas of **Counter Terrorism & Intelligence; Communications, Command and Control; Covert Operations and Capabilities; and Border and Maritime security.** Furthermore, these areas were also strongly correlated with each other, as well as **Data Acquisition and Analysis.**

Figure 1 - Number of exhibitors aligned to each product and service category (each can be aligned to multiple areas)

Alongside the exhibition, a speaker programme comprising almost 60 sessions explored 17 key topics, highlighting the nexus between technology, operational challenges, capabilities, and opportunities.

Artificial Intelligence	Horizon Europe	Training
Biometrics	Innovation & Emerging Threats	Transformation
Border security	Legislative framework	Video Analytics
Digital Era	Partnership	Violence against communities
Fire / First responder	Public safety	Violent crime
Forensics	Strategy	

Security & Policing is a major event with numerous official delegations from across the world. The event sees participation from across UK Government including Border Force, Defence Science and Technology Laboratory (DSTL), Forensic Capability Network (FCN), National Crime Agency (NCA), National Counter Terrorism Security Office (NaCTSO), Law Enforcement Data Service (LEDS), National CBRN Centre, Joint Maritime Security Centre, UK Space Agency and several Home Office departments.

Home Office Security & Policing 2025: Exhibitors

The 2025 edition of Security & Policing hosted **434 organisations**, showcasing a strong representation from the private sector with **401 companies**, and confirming the event's role as a key marketplace for security innovation. With **25 countries represented**, it remains strongly UK-focused with **353 organizations originating from the UK**. Furthermore, the event also had exhibitors from **19 European countries** representing 53 different organizations. This concentration reflects the UK Home Office's effort to create a nationwide platform that fosters cooperation and opportunities for the security and policing industry, while also offering valuable space for international engagement and collaboration.

Policy areas

Security & Policing is strongly aligned with European Union priorities in the field of security, with 354 organisations offering a service or product related to at least one of the following areas from the EU security market taxonomy: fighting organised crime, terrorism and radicalisation, cybercrime, or horizontal and societal issues linked to crime.

In detail, within the field of organised crime, 92 organisations offered products or services targeting human and goods trafficking, while 43 addressed cargo crime. Regarding terrorism and radicalisation, 120 organisations focused on the protection of public spaces, and 89 offered solutions for preventing or investigating CBRN threats. In the area of cybercrime, 88 organisations provided capabilities related to encryption, and 51 addressed other cyber-related issues such as covert operations, lawful interception, and data acquisition. Finally, 90 organisations were involved in community policing, and 26 focused on travel intelligence, including PNR systems, dog detection, and x-ray security imaging - contributing to horizontal and societal security issues.

Figure 2 - Alignment of exhibitors with the level 2 (yellow) and level 3 (blue) categories of the EU security market taxonomy policy areas

Functions Areas

Regarding the specific functions of the products and services on display from the exhibitors, there are two clear tracks of solutions promoted through the event – the first on the digital side under **data, information & intelligence gathering management and exploitation** and the second on **personal and other equipment for prevention, response and recovery** indicating an interesting split between computer-based and field activities. Interestingly, **physical access** control solutions were also prevalent alongside **training and exercises**. This again shows that, compared to SICUR, TECNOSEC and EUROSATORY, the profile of exhibitors can depend on national and event priorities, which can be helpful for attendees to identify the event most aligned with their needs.

Figure 3 – Alignment of exhibitors with the functions areas of the EU security market taxonomy

Technology areas

Regarding technology areas, 153 organisations are supplying general-purpose equipment, making it the most represented category. Additionally, 134 organisations are involved in **training, simulation, or capacity-building activities**, underlining the importance of skills development alongside technical innovation. **Surveillance systems** also stand out, with 108 organisations offering solutions in this domain, ranging from video analytics to integrated monitoring platforms. These figures highlight the central role of foundational technologies and operational readiness in addressing the evolving challenges of internal security.

Figure 4 – Alignment of exhibitors with the technology areas of the EUCS taxonomy policy areas

Overall, companies at Security & Policing 2025 offer a diverse range of products, services, and skills, with an average of **7.6 areas of expertise per organisation**. Many of these areas are naturally interconnected, such as **surveillance systems, tracking solutions, monitoring tools, guarding, physical protection, and access control**, reflecting integrated approaches to security delivery. This diversity highlights the evolving complexity of the internal security market, where multi-domain capabilities are increasingly valued. Notably, there is a significant gap between the 124 organisations that specialise in only 1 to 4 areas of expertise—often start-ups or small and medium-sized enterprises—and the 41 organisations offering products and services across more than 15 distinct policy or technology domains. This contrast suggests a dual market structure: on one side, agile niche providers; on the other, mature companies with wide-ranging portfolios. Together, they contribute to a dynamic innovation ecosystem, balancing depth in specialised capabilities with scalability across operational needs.

Home Office Security & Policing 2025: Speaker Programme

Together with the exhibition booths, Security & Policing also gathered key stakeholders from government, law enforcement, academia, and industry to explore current and emerging challenges in homeland security. There were 58 speaker sessions at Security & Policing 2025 addressing 17 distinct topics, ranging from public safety and violent crime to biometrics, AI, and digital transformation. Special attention was given to innovation-driven partnerships, operational resilience, and the integration of new technologies into policing and national security strategies. The full conference programme has been reviewed and mapped to the policy, functions, and technology taxonomy.

Of the 58 sessions held during Security & Policing 2025, a clear strategic orientation emerged: 18 conferences focused on **innovation**—both as an opportunity, a challenge, or a threat—while 17 addressed **partnerships**, often between government and industry in areas such as counterterrorism, cybercrime, or emerging threats. **Police transformation**—whether through public procurement, legislative evolution, or resilience—was also a key theme in 16 sessions. In terms of threats and security functions, **protection of public spaces** stood out with 17 sessions, reflecting a sustained effort to combat knife crime in urban environments and terrorism. **Digital forensics** and the broader use of data for criminal analysis and video analytics were covered in 13 sessions, highlighting their growing importance. Finally, six sessions directly addressed **disinformation and deepfake technologies**—an emerging concern for law enforcement and security services across Europe, particularly in combating deepfakes and other threats posed by generative AI.

Relevant insights

Security & Policing is one of the largest security-related conferences and exhibitions in the UK, recognised for the large number of exhibitors showcasing innovations from UK companies and organizations, whilst also hosting many international delegations indicating the relevance of these products and services well beyond the United Kingdom. As mentioned, its closed-door nature helps to build an environment for secure and trusted information sharing and in-depth conversations between public and private organizations, with all those present working towards a shared vision and common goal of enhancing national security and resilience.

In addition to the individually prevalent categories in the policy areas, reviewing how different policy, functions and technology areas interact also yields new insights, for example, the strong alignment between trafficking of humans and goods with cargo crime, travel intelligence and community policing, or the protection of public spaces with the detection of explosive precursors, or more interestingly with encryption and 5G technologies. This indicates an increase in overlapping areas of interest. Similarly, these two areas draw on a strong alignment with particular functions areas, especially personal and other equipment, data, information and intelligence, monitoring and surveillance systems. Furthermore, products and services related to trafficking also strongly correlate with screening and detection tools, which are also closely linked to CBRN threats. Other areas which showed intersections included community policing and training and simulation, perhaps indicating a growth area for this type of technology.

Compared to previous reports on TECNOSEC, SICUR and EUROSATORY, Security and Policing was more similar to EUROSATORY in terms of the high prevalence of the functions area of training and exercises and training and simulation technology. Closer alignment with TECNOSEC is seen through the high number of visitors demonstrating surveillance-related technologies, while products and services related to encryption and 5G were more common than in other events, which could represent a move towards such technologies being more market-ready as well as the market itself showing a greater business need for products in such areas.

The conference programme including awards for both industry and academic innovation, and key speakers from government, public services and industry, also provided a unique platform for understanding current market needs and a look towards the innovations needed in the future for organizations to continue to meet the needs of the security and policing sector.

Home Office Security & Policing 2025: reference information

Name of the event: Home Office Security & Policing, The Official UK Government Global Security Event

Dates: 11 March – 13 March 2025

Location: Farnborough International Exhibition and Conference Centre, United Kingdom

Website: <https://www.securityandpolicing.co.uk/>

Security and Policing 2026	
10-12 March 2026	Farnborough International Exhibition and Conference Centre, UK

ENACT.

European Network Against
Crime and Terrorism

[@enact-network](https://www.linkedin.com/company/enact-network)

enact-eu.net

Scan the QR code to visit ENACT online
and read this report in digital format.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

